

“Performance of Weather Based Crop Insurance Scheme: A Case Study of Banana Crop in Selected Districts of Karnataka”

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G.S. Ashalatha

*Research Scholar, J.S.S. Research Foundation
J.S.S. Technical Institution Campus, S.J.C.E- Mysuru*

Dr. M. Prabhu

*Research Guide, J.S.S. Research Foundation
J.S.S. Technical Institution Campus, S.J.C.E- Mysuru*

Abstract

Among the tropical Horticultural crops, Bananna which is known as Berry a native of Indumalaya and Austrelia widely cultivated in 135 countries. It is first introduced to India in 327 B.C. by Alexander the Great. Then onwards it has a significant place in Indian agriculture as it widely used all over India for all kinds of religious rituals as well as a nutritious food. Banana (Musa sp.) is the second most important fruit crop in India next to mango. Its year round availability, affordability, varietal range, taste, nutritive and medicinal value makes it has the favourite fruit among all classes of people. It has also good export potential of domestic production only 0.05% is exported and the rest is consumed within the country mostly as a table fruit. India exports bananas mainly to Middle East countries viz. U.A.E., Saudi Arabia, Oman, Bahrain, Qatar. The varieties which are in demand internationally include Grand Naine and Cavendish. Hi-tech cultivation of the crop is an economically viable enterprise leading to increase in productivity, improvement in produce quality and early crop maturity with the produce commanding premium price.

Introduction

Agriculture is the back bone of Indian economy not only plays an important role in agriculture but also plays an important role in the field of commerce. Nearly 40% of the Indian exports constitute the agricultural products. The Indian agricultural products constitute Food, Commercial, Plantation and Horticultural crops, but the success of the Indian agriculture depends on weather and rainfall factors. One of the noticeable factors in the Indian economy is that the share of the agriculture to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is gradually coming down in the country but retains an important role in the economic development of the country. Horticultural crops such as Banana, Coconut, Tomaoto, Potato, Cabeage, Brinjal, Beans etc. are occupied very less percent of total production area whereas Food crops, and Cereals and Plantation crops are occupied a major portion.

Among the tropical Horticultural crops, Banana which is known as Berry a native of Indumalaya and Austrelia widely cultivated in 135 countries. It is first introduced to India in 327 B.C. by Alexander the Great. Then onwards it has a significant place in Indian agriculture as it widely used all over India for all kinds of religious rituals as well as a nutritious food. Banana (*Musa sp.*) is the second most important fruit crop in India next to mango. Its year round availability, affordability, varietal range, taste, nutritive and medicinal value makes it has the favourite fruit among all classes of people. It has also good export potential of domestic production only 0.05% is exported and the rest is consumed within the country mostly as a table fruit. India exports bananas mainly to Middle East countries viz. U.A.E., Saudi Arabia, Oman, Bahrain, Qatar. The varieties which are in demand internationally include Grand Naine and Cavendish. Hi-tech cultivation of the crop is an economically viable enterprise leading to increase in productivity, improvement in produce quality and early crop maturity with the produce commanding premium price.

Banana now is considered as one of the important commercial crops annually cultivated in an area of 830.5 thousand hectares and the production is around 2779.91 thousand tone. It is widely cultivated in the states (Table-1) of Maharastra, Tamil Nadu, Gujarat, Karnataka and Andrapredesh.

Banana Crop Cultivation and Agro-climatic Requirements

In Karnataka (table-1) Banana is cultivated in an area of 13.46% and produces nearly 7.66% of the total countries production (62765 hectares and produces 124448 tonnes) with an average yield of 19821 kg/hectares. The important varieties are Robusta, Rasthali, Poovan, Monthan, Elakkibale.

Table 1 Area, Production and Productivity in India

States	Area in 000 ha	Production in 000 MT	Productivity HA/MT
Tamil Nadu	15.06	27.71	65.8
Maharashtra	9.878	14.44	52.5
Gujarat	7.798	13.35	61.5
Karnataka	13.461	7.66	20.4
Andra Pradesh	9.54	9.31	35.0
Madya Pradesh	4.58	5.77	45.2
Bihar	3.82	5.09	47.6
Uttar Pradesh	3.90	4.51	41.5
WB	5.057	3.391	24.0
Assam	5.73	2.43	15.2
Others	21.10	6.28	10.7
Total	100.00	100.00	

Source: agriexcchange.apeda.geo.in Agri

Commercially, bananas are classified as dessert types and culinary types. The culinary types have starchy fruits and are used in the mature unripe form as vegetables. Important cultivars include Robusta, Monthan, Poovan, Nendran, Red banana, Nyali, Safed Velchi, Basrai, Ardhapuri, Rasthali, Karpurvalli, Karthali and Grand Naine etc. Grand Naine, an imported variety from Israel is gaining popularity and may soon become the most preferred variety due to its tolerance to abiotic stresses and good quality bunches. Fruit develops attractive uniform yellow colour with better shelf life & quality than other cultivars.

Area, Production and Yield of Banana Crop in Karnataka

In Karnataka Banana is cultivated in an area of 62765 hectares. It is widely cultivated crop concentrated in all most all the district of the state with production of 124448 tonnes having an average yield of 19821 Kg/hectares where as Koppala records highest of 74549 Kg/hectares and Dhakhinakanada records least of 2814 Kg/hectares. Nearly more than 40% of the area and 45% of the production (table-2) under banana crop is concentrated within five districts of the state. The main districts under the banana cultivated area are Mysore (11.04%), followed by Shimogha (8.78%), Tumukuru (8.28%) Hassan (5.67%) and Dakshinakannada (5.21%). The production is highest in Chickamangaluru (10.49%) followed by Mysuru (9.60%), Koppala (8.93%), Tumukuru (8.10%) and Hasssan (7.74%) least in Yadgiri, followed by Raichur district both in area and production.

Table 2 Area, Production and Yield of Banana for the year 2016 in Karnataka

Sl.No	District	Area	Percentage	Production	Percentage	Yield
1	Bagalkote	1051	1.68	50897	4.09	48427
2	Bangalore - Urban	440	0.71	8721	0.70	19821
3	Bangalore - Rural	1070	1.71	16216	1.30	15155
4	Belgaum	1775	2.83	60306	4.85	33975
5	Bellary	2594	4.14	21771	1.75	8393
6	Bidar	280	0.45	5550	0.45	19821
7	Bijapur	1578	2.52	30323	2.44	19216
8	Chamarajanagar	2917	4.65	53784	4.32	18438
9	Chickballapur	2862	4.56	130556	10.49	45617
10	Chikmagalur	3204	5.11	24075	1.94	7514
11	Chitradurga	2724	4.34	51593	4.15	18940
12	Dakshina Kannada	3274	5.22	9213	0.74	2814
13	Davanagere	2402	3.83	50444	4.05	21001
14	Dharwad	188	0.30	3726	0.30	19821
15	Gadag	285	0.46	5649	0.45	19821
16	Gulbarga	1681	2.68	32640	2.62	19417
17	Hassan	3560	5.68	96412	7.75	27082
18	Haveri	1317	2.10	67297	5.41	51099
19	Kodagu	1982	3.16	8766	0.70	4423
20	Kolar	583	0.10	21750	1.75	37307
21	Koppal	1491	2.34	111153	8.93	74549
22	Mandya	1911	3.05	33154	2.67	17349
23	Mysore	6934	11.05	119494	9.61	17233
24	Raichur	146	0.24	2894	0.23	19821

25	Ramanagar	2005	3.20	53189	4.28	26528
26	Shimoga	5517	8.79	40760	3.28	7388
27	Tumkur	5203	8.29	100881	8.11	19389
28	Udupi	1047	1.67	14699	1.18	14039
29	Uttara Kannada	2690	4.29	17065	1.37	6344
30	Yadgir	54	0.09	1070	0.09	19821
State Total		62765	100	1244048	100	19821

Source: Directorate of Economics and Statistics

Agro-climatic requirements

Banana, basically a tropical crop, as well mentioned in the table -3 it grows well in a temperature range of 15°C – 35°C with relative humidity of 75-85%. It prefers tropical humid lowlands and is grown from the sea level to an elevation of 2000 mts. above MSL. In India this crop is being cultivated in climate ranging from humid tropical to dry mild subtropics through selection of appropriate varieties. Chilling injury occurs at temperature below 12°C. High velocity of wind which exceeds 80 km /hr. damages the crop. Four months of monsoon (June to September) with an average 650-750 mm. rainfall are most important for vigorous vegetative growth of banana. At higher altitudes, banana cultivation is restricted to a few varieties like ‘Hill banana’. The wind prone areas cause devastating damage to the banana plantations by toppling down the plants due to pseudo stem breakage. Similarly, bananas cannot withstand frost to any extent. So, at higher elevations the low temperatures prevailing cause delayed cropping and slow growth.

Deep, rich loamy soil with pH 6.5 to 7.5 is most preferred for banana cultivation. Soil for banana should have good drainage, adequate fertility and moisture. Saline solid, calcareous soils are not suitable for banana cultivation. A soil which is neither too acidic nor too alkaline, rich in organic material with high nitrogen content, adequate phosphorus level and plenty of potash is good for banana.

Table 3 Climatic Requirements for Banana

Factors	Banana Crop
1. Elevation	2000m.
2. Temperature	15°C – 35°C
3. Relative humidity	75-85%.
4. Annual rainfall	650-750 mm.
5. Velocity of wind	80 km /hr. damages the crop
6. Soil	Deep, rich loamy soil with pH between 6.5 to 7.5

Source: Horticultural Department

Weather based Crop Insurance for Banana

In India agriculture insurance company introduced several insurance schemes for agriculture; there are no such insurance schemes available for Banana till 2007. For the first time in the history of Banana the Agriculture Insurance Company introduced the Weather Insurance Scheme for Banana cultivators in the year 2007. It is a unique Weather insurance product specially designed for the banana growers of Karnataka. This product is designed to cover risk that arises out of weather failures such as Rainfall, (Deficit rainfall, Consecutive Dry Days (CDD), Rainy Days, Excess rainfall, Consecutive Wet Days (CWD) Temperature, (Max. Temperature (heat), Min. Temperature (frost), Mean Temperature), Hourly Chilling units Relative Humidity and Wind

Speed is expected to provide effective risk management aid to those banana cultivators likely to be impacted by adverse weather condition. The most important benefits of WBCI are:

- a) Trigger events like adverse weather can be independently verified and measured.
- b) Parameters considered in designing this insurance product are relevant, appropriate and to a large extent captures the weather induced risks affecting banana crop.
- c) Allows for speedy settlement of indemnities.

The policy compensates the insured, against the likelihood of diminished banana output / yield resulting from weather disturbances occurred within a specific geographical location and specified time period, subject to a maximum of the Sum Insured specified in the policy under each of the coverage options Period of Insurance. This scheme (table-4) is launched with a view to protect the banana growers since 2007 from weather risk.

Table 4 Weather based Corp. Insurance Scheme Term Sheet

Weather Based Crop Insurance Scheme					
Term Sheet			Season		
1.	State: A District: B Tehsil: C				
	Crop : D		RAU: E		
	Reference Weather Station: F				
	Deficit Rainfall				
			Phase-I	Phase-II	Phase-III
	Rainfall Volume	Period	15th June to 20th July	21st July to 20th August	21st August to 25th September
		Trigger	50 mm	80 mm	80mm
	No. of Consecutive Dry Days				
		Rainfall Distribution (Consecutive Dry Days)	PERIOD	1st July to 5th September	
			Trigger Days (>=) 20	24	
Note : Rainfall of less than 2.5mm in a day shall not be considered as a rainy day					
2.		Excess Rainfall on a Single Day	Period	15th July to 15th August	
			Trigger (>)	200 mm	

If rainfall period is from 15th July to 31st October, the requirement of rain (water) by the crop plant may also vary fortnightly (i.e. 15-31st July, 1-15th August, 16-31st August, 1-15th September and so on) or monthly or such other period that the State Government decides on prevailing weather condition.

Termsheet for Weather Based Crop Insurance Scheme

- CROP : A
 STATE : B
 District : C
 Tehsil : D
 Reference Weather Station : E (IMD)

Index – A (Excess Rainfall Cover)			
Maximum of cumulative rainfall in mm of any 2 consecutive days during the cover period			
Cover Phase, From	15-Jul	1-Sept	1-Oct
To	31-Aug	30-Sept	31-Oct
Strike 1 (mm)	80	33	15
Strike 2 (mm)	175	95	45
Exit (mm)	285	200	134
Standard Loss Rate between Strike 1 and Strike 2 – Notional 1 (Rs./mm/Hectare)	20.91	24.76	30.45
Policy Limit (Rs/Hectare)	3000	3000	3000
Index B (Deficit Rainfall Cover)			
Aggregate rainfall during the cover phases in mm			
Cover Phase, From		25-Jun	16-Aug
To		15-Aug	30-Sept
Strike 1 (mm)		475	200
Strike 2 (mm)		270	95
Exit (mm)		25	10
Standard Loss Rate between Strike 1 and Strike 2 – Notional 1 (Rs./mm/Hectare)		7	21
Policy Limit (Rs/Hectare)		24	62
		7500	7500

Index C (Consecutive Dry Days)	
Maximum Number of Consecutive Dry Days (CDD) where dry day is a day with rainfall less than equal to 2.5mm	
Cover Phase, From	15- July
To	31-August
Strike 1 (CDD's)	4
Strike 2 (CDD's)	10
Strike 3 (CDD's)	14
Strike 4 (CDD's)	19
Exit (CDD's)	24
Payout 1 (Rs/Hectare) for Strike 1 < CDD <=Strike 2	328
Payout2 (Rs/Hectare) for Strike 1 < CDD <=Strike 3	720
Payout3 (Rs/Hectare) for Strike 1 < CDD <=Strike 4	1800
Payout4 (Rs/Hectare) for Strike 1 < CDD <=Exit	3600
Maximum Payout (RS/Hectare) for CDD > Exit	6000
Combined Policy Limit (Rs/Hectare) – Say	30,000
Premium (Rs/Hectare) say	3,000
Farmer's Share (Rs/Hectare) say	750

Backup reference Weather Stations: X

Date Source: IMD / Independent third party like NCMSL, SKYMET, etc.

Settlement Date: Within Thirty days from the data released by data provider.

Insured Banana growers in Karnataka

A total of 1,27,487 insured farmers are engaged in Banana cultivation in Karnataka (table-5), of which more than 50% of the farmers are from five districts and remaining 25 districts covered less than 50%. The thing to be noticed is that the major five districts who have enrolled for weather insurance are not either major cultivated districts or the producers except Shimogha in cultivated area and Tumukur both in area and production. Haveri stands first with 12.33% followed by Shimogha, Tumkur, Chikkamagaluru and Dharwad district with 11.10%, 11.05%, 9.05% and 7.54% respectively. Bangalore Urban (0.14%), Chikamaagaluru (0.34%), Bengaluru Rural (0.39%), Bhagalakote (0.70%) and Chamarajanagara (0.92%) districts records least in the enrolment.

Table 5 District wise Insurance Enrolment Status Report on 13-07-2016

Sl.No	Name of the District	Total	
1	Bagalkot	904	0.71
2	Bengaluru urban	186	0.15
3	Bengaluru rural	507	0.40
4	Belagavi	2231	1.75
5	Ballari	2269	1.78
6	Bidar	1408	1.11
7	Bijayapura	2377	1.87
8	Chamrajnagar	1179	0.93
9	Chikkaballapur	445	0.35
10	Chikkamagaluru	11542	9.06
11	Chitradurga	3690	2.90
12	Dakshinakannada	3985	3.13
13	Davangere	5321	4.18
14	Dharwad	9621	7.55
15	Gadag	5723	4.49
16	Gulbarga	3302	2.60
17	Hassan	7416	5.82
18	Haveri	15723	12.34
19	Kodagu	3312	2.60
20	Kolar	1897	1.49
21	Koppal	1470	1.16
22	Mandya	1390	1.10
23	Mysuru	2384	1.87
24	Raichur	2662	2.09
25	Ramanagara	716	0.57
26	Shivamogga	14158	11.11
27	Tumkuru	14036	11.01
28	Udupi	2062	1.62
29	Uttarkannada	3991	3.14
30	Yadgiri	1580	1.24
Total		127487	100

Report generated by: ddh_mysuru(mysuru)

The Problem

As a commercial and a horticultural crop banana plays an important role in the Indian agriculture especially in the Mysuru district of Karnataka. The cultivation of banana is not so easy as its success depends upon several weather phenomena specially the initial rainfall and subsequently to high velocity wind during the monsoon season. The problem with farmers is how to handle the weather risk. The proper weather insurance which covers the adverse impact of weather is the only solution to the farmers.

Review of Literature

Climate plays a dominant role in the success of Indian agriculture. It contributes to richness or poverty of farmers directly or indirectly. Actual losses from weather disturbances causes crisis to the farmers. The threat may occur when a weather disturbance destroys farmer's crops which will lead the family of farmers go hungry and bankruptcy leading to sell their animals and belongings in order to survive.

Review of available literature is an important and integral part of research. It will help in framing the aims objectives and methodology and helps in identifying research gaps of the subject and need for the present study. The review of past research studies relevant to the present has been collected from International, National and regional studies.

Akyoo, et.al. (2013)¹ their study was to assess prevailing risks, coping strategies and their effectiveness in managing crop losses due to natural weather hazards, and potential for crop insurance for bean farmers in Arumeru district in Arusha region of Tanzania during the 2003/04 crop season . The study recommended the need to mount a crop insurance pilot program which would be initially funded by the Government, of specific peril and voluntary. This should go in tandem with introduction of insurance training in agricultural schools and colleges to increase its awareness to the target populace.

Gurdev Singh (2010)² discussed the crop Insurance in India and the dependence of Indian agriculture on uncertain rains. He argues on the need for crop insurance as an alternative to manage production risk and discusses at length the two important products, namely, National Agricultural Insurance Scheme and Weather Based Insurance Scheme. It also reflects on some deficiencies in this product.

Lopamudra Mohapatra& R K Dhaliwal (2014)³ examined the various agricultural schemes operating in the state of Punjab microscopically and macroscopically in the country. The study concludes with the findings that the major insurance running in the country is NAIS but was not Punjab state since the paddy and wheat crops grown in the state are less risky crop in the wake of assured irrigation and high input agriculture. Weather based insurance products have got a good scope in the state to act as a tool of risk mitigation.

McIntosh. et.al. (2013)⁴ explore the relationship between fertilizer use and the demand for Weather Index Insurance (WII) among smallholder farmers in Ethiopia. They examine whether fertilizer use is portable under current smallholder production conditions, whether risk-related

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1. Akyoo, A.M.et.al.,(2013) 'Agricultural production risks, coping mechanisms and potential for crop insurance in Tanzania'. Time Journals of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences Vol. 1(1) pp.11-22 July 2013.
 2. Gurdev Singh (2010)'Crop Insurance in India' Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad India Research and Publications W.P. No. 2010-06-01 June 2010
 3. Lopamudra Mohapatra& R K Dhaliwal (2014), 'Review of Agricultural Insurance in Punjab State of India' International Journal of Advanced Research (2014), Volume 2, Issue 5, 459-467.
 4. McIntosh.C. et.al., (2013) 'Productivity, credit, risk, and the demand for weather index insurance in smallholder agriculture in Ethiopia'. Agricultural Economics 44 (2013) 399-417.

factors affect fertilizer use, and they also estimate the returns to inputs in the agricultural production function in the absence of insurance.

Michael Carter. et.al (2014)⁵ is of opinion that the index-based weather insurance is a major institutional innovation that could revolutionize access to formal insurance for millions of smallholder farmers and related individuals. Significant efforts have been made in research to assess its impacts on shock coping and risk management, and to contribute to improvements in design and implementation.

Prabhu.. et.al.,(2012)⁶ have explored the impact of basis risk on the performance of Rainfall Insurance Scheme for Coffee in Karnataka. The study is based on core findings of a pilot study that addresses the current gap in the understanding of basis risk and performance of rainfall insurance. It is particularly valuable for both the growers and insurance company. Quantitative design method was adopted with some qualitative elements with a sample field survey of 240 growers who have purchased the rainfall insurance contracts. Correlation and regression analyze were used to test the performance of RISC programme in view of plausible negative impact of basis risk. The study highlights the problem of basis risk and the effects on the performance of RISC. The findings reveal the need for initiating steps to minimize basis risk.

Prabhu..et.al., (2015)⁷ have explored the factors influencing the design and the development of rainfall index insurance scheme for coffee plantation the method used isqualitivedesign with some Quantitative elements data were collected through a field survey of 390 growers who have purchased the rainfall insurance contracts factor analysis principal component analysis Kaiser – Meyer Olkin, Bartlett's test of Sphericity Kaiser Varimax rotation were used to measure the sample adequacy and to extract the factors affecting the rainfall index insurance. In this study several variable impacting the rainfall index insurance have been identified for factor analysis on the basis VarimaxKaiser Normalisation eight factors have emerged this include rainfall risk trigger rainfall sum insured, rainfall risk protection, basis risk, claim settlement, payout and premium. The findings revealed the need for redesigned and recasting excising rainfall insurance scheme for efficient risk management in coffee industry.

Sreejamol.K.S. (2016)⁸ aims to analyze the awareness of policy holders towards Weather Based Crop Insurance Schemes in Kollengode taluk of Palakkad district in Kerala because the climate of this district is slightly different from the rest of the State, as it is influenced by the presence of Palakkad gap. The study concludes with the findings that the weather based crop insurance Scheme is available to all kinds of farmers. However those who have taken farm- loans from financial institutions are covered compulsorily, but still the farmers are having very limited knowledge about the scheme. Panchayati Raj, banks (both cooperative banks as well as commercial banks) Insurance companies should motivate and to educate farmers to take the policy and the pros and cons of the scheme.

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5. Michael Carter. et.al., (2014) 'Index-based weather insurance for developing countries: A review of evidence and a set of propositions for up-scaling' Background document for the workshop: "Microfinance products for weather risk management in developing countries: State of the arts and perspectives" Paris, June 25 2014
 6. Prabhu. M. et.al. (2012) Impact of basis risk on the performance of rainfall insurance scheme for coffee: a perceptual analysis International journal of research in commerce & management Volume no. 3 (2012), issue no. 1 (January) ISSN 0976-2183
 7. Prabhu. M. et.al. (2015) Rainfall insurance scheme for coffee in Karnataka: Exploring the indicators of performance. International journal of Banking Risk and Insurance. Volume no. 3 (2015), issue no. 1
 8. Sreejamol.K.S. (2016) 'Weather based crop insurance scheme - A study on the awareness of the farmers (Policyholders) towards the scheme in Palakkad district'. IJAR 2016; 2(5): 377-379

Research Gap

The above survey of related literature emphasis more on the performance and evaluation of different insurance scheme especially weather based crop insurance schemes in India and abroad and the salient features of each of them but none of them related to Karnataka or Mysuru especially regarding the Horticultural crop Banana. These studies were concerned with the suggestions and recommendations for the further study with this backdrop an attempt is made to study the performance of weather based crop insurance for Banana in Mysuru district of Karnataka. .

References

1. Akyoo, A.M.et.al.,(2013) ‘Agricultural production risks, coping mechanisms and potential for crop insurance in Tanzania’. Time Journals of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences, Vol. 1(1) pp.11-22 July 2013.
2. Barnett.B.J. and Mahul.O (2008), “Weather Index Insurance for Agriculture and Rural Areas in Lower Income Countries”.
3. Gunnar Breustedt.et.al.,(2008)‘Evaluating the Potential of Index Insurance Schemes to Reduce Crop Yield Risk in an Arid Region’. Journal of Agricultural Economics, Vol. 59, No. 2, 2008, 312–328.
4. Gurdev Singh (2010)‘Crop Insurance in India’ Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad India Research and Publications W.P. No. 2010-06-01 June 2010.
5. Lopamudra Mohapatra& R K Dhaliwal (2014),‘Review of Agricultural Insurance in Punjab State of India’International Journal of Advanced Research (2014), Volume 2, Issue 5, 459-467.
6. Mafoua, E. K. and Turvey, C. G (2003) ‘Weather Insurance to Protect Specialty Crops against Costs of Irrigation in Drought Years’ Paper prepared for presentation at the American Agricultural Economic Association Annual Meeting, Montreal, Canada, July 27-30 2003.
7. McIntosh.C. et.al., (2013) ‘Productivity, credit, risk, and the demand for weather index insurance in smallholder agriculture in Ethiopia’. Agricultural Economics 44 (2013) 399–417.
8. Michael Carter. et.al., (2014)‘Index-based weather insurance for developing countries: A review of evidence and a set of propositions for up-scaling’ Background document for the workshop: “Microfinance products for weather risk management in developing countries: State of the arts and perspectives” Paris, June 25 2014.
9. Prabhu. M. et.al. (2012), Impact of basis risk on the performance of rainfall insurance scheme for coffee: a perceptual analysisInternational journal of research in commerce & managementVolume no. 3 (2012), issue no. 1 (January) ISSN 0976-2183.
10. Prabhu. M. et.al. (2015) Rainfall insurance scheme for coffee in Karnataka: Exploring the indicators of performance. International journal of Banking Risk and Insurance. Volume no. 3 (2015), issue no. 1.
11. Rao and Bockel (2008) “Risk Management as a Pillar in Agriculture and Food Security Policies”: India case study Policy Brief Easypol Module 2009.
12. Skees. J.R, Goes. A, Sullivan.C, Carpenter.R, Miranda.M, and Barnett.B.J(2006), “Indexinsurance for weather risk in lower-income countries”, World Bank projects on agricultural risk management Global Ag Risk, Inc.,
13. Sreejamol.K.S. (2016) ‘Weather based crop insurance scheme - A study on the awareness of the farmers (Policyholders) towards the scheme in Palakkad district’. IJAR 2016; 2(5): 377-379.
14. Syroka.J, World Bank (2007), “Experiences in Index-Based Weather Insurance for Farmers: Lessons Learnt from India & Malawi”, Innovative Finance Meeting, New York, 18th October 2007.